

- RQ1:
 - **py RQ1_see_result.py** to see the results
 - enter **sub id** of subcategories to enter next level
 - enter **-1** to return to father category
 - for every category marked (xxx/xxx), means (matching nodes / all nodes)
 - visit_wiki_final_splitroot_cs.txt : Wikipedia categories and pages with mark of whether matched

- RQ2:

- **py RQ2_plot.py** to see the results
 - edit this part to change class you want to visualize

```
labels=labels5
keys=keys5
key_class='5'
fileinName='RQ2.txt'
fileoutName='pic/'+key_class+'.png'
picname="Topic analysis for class "+key_class
```

- edit **key_class, keys, labels**
- RQ2.txt : samples and marked topics for every class of repositories, it's a json format file.
 - for every repository in samples, we have:
 - name of the repository
 - description of the repository
 - topics of the repository
 - topics are marked as "topic_name type_list" as "typescript 0"
 - *for different class of repositories, types and labels are mapped differently*
 - check detailed information of mapping tags and types in RQ2_plot.py

- RQ3:

- **py RQ3_visualize.py** to visualize
- RQ3_samples100_1_20_marked.txt,
- RQ3_samples100_20_40_marked.txt,
- RQ3_samples100_40_more_marked.txt
 - above txt files are samples for RQ3 analysis, 100 users in each file
 - for every user
 - name on Stack Overflow
 - topics extracted from repositories of themselves
 - toptags extracted from Stack Overflow
 - top tag marked as

- "0 xx" means it matched directly
- "2 xx" means it matched indirectly
- "1 xx" means it unmatched

- RQ4

- **py RQ4_plot_issues.py or RQ4_plot_stars.py** to visualize
- organizationRepsJsonIssuesUpdated.txt
 - repositories used in RQ4 analysis
 - "login": organization name
 - "githubReps": their repository list
 - "stargazers_count": number of stars
 - "issues_updated_at": last updated time of issues